

Knowledge Networks in Biomedical and Behavioral Research

May 28-29, 2025

6001 Executive Blvd, Rockville, MD 20852

Meeting Agenda

Day 1 – Wednesday, May 28, 2025	
7:45am – 10:00am	Opening Session
7:45am – 8:30am	Breakfast and Registration
8:30am – 8:40am	Welcome and Introduction [slides] Cathy Wu & Chunlei Wu, Meeting Co-Chairs
8:40am – 9:00am	Opening Remarks [slides] Dr. Nicole Kleinstreuer, Acting NIH Deputy Director for Program Coordination, Planning, and Strategic Initiatives (Introduced by Dr. Susan Gregurick, ODSS Director [slides])
9:00am – 9:45am	Keynote [slides] Dr. Chaitan Baru, Senior Advisor, Directorate for Technology, Innovation, and Partnerships (TIP), National Science Foundation (Introduced by Dr. Susan Gregurick)
9:45am – 10:00am	Break
10:00am – 1:00pm	Session 1: Desiderata of Biomedical Knowledge Networks - Inference, Validation, and AI Integration [slides]
10:00am – 10:15am	Introduction Hongfang Liu & Jason Flannick, Session Co-Leads
10:15am – 11:15am	Panel Presentation and Discussion Deanne Taylor, Bian Jiang, Chris Bizon, Licong Cui
11:15am – 11:30am	Break
11:30am – 12:30pm	Break Out Sessions
12:30pm – 1:00pm	Report Out and Discussion
1:00pm – 2:00pm	Lunch on Your Own
2:00pm – 5:00pm	Session 2: Building Interoperable and Reusable Knowledge Networks: Standards, Ontologies, and Governance [slides]

2:00pm – 2:15pm	Introduction Mark Musen & Andrew Su, Session Co-Leads
2:15pm – 3:15pm	Panel Presentation and Discussion Chris Mungall, Chunhua Weng, Katy Börner, Jeffrey Grethe
3:15pm – 3:30pm	Break
3:30pm – 4:30pm	Break Out Sessions
4:30pm – 5:00pm	Report Out and Discussion
Day 2 – Thursday, May 29, 2025	
8:00am – 9:45am	Opening Session
8:00am - 8:30am	Breakfast and Registration
8:30am - 8:45am	Introduction [slides] Chunlei Wu & Cathy Wu, Meeting Co-Chairs
8:45am - 9:30am	Keynote [slides] Mr. Adam Bly, founder and CEO of System Inc. (Introduced by Dr. Susan Gregurick)
9:30am – 9:45am	Break
9:45am – 12:45pm	Session 3: Constructing Trustworthy, Safe, and Secure Knowledge Networks [slides]
9:45am – 10:00am	Introduction Larry Hunter & Thomas Powers, Session Co-Leads
10:00am – 11:00am	Panel Presentation and Discussion Melissa Haendel, Nick Evans, Katy Börner, Jonathan Silverstein
11:00am – 11:15am	Break
11:15am – 12:15pm	Break Out Sessions
12:15pm – 12:45pm	Report Out and Discussion
12:45pm – 2:00pm	Lunch on Your Own
2:00pm – 4:00pm	NIH Team & Co-Chairs/Co-Leads Working Session – Draft Report